
Firm Attributes and Share Price of Quoted Firms in Nigeria: Analysis of Investors' Evaluations of Financial and Non-Financial Sectors

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Abstract

Purpose: This study investigates how firm attributes influence the share price of quoted firms in Nigeria across financial and non-financial sectors. It examines the impact of firm age, audit firm size, earnings per share (EPS), firm size, leverage, and industry type on stock valuation.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Using a panel dataset of 1,800 firm-year observations (2006–2023), the study applies the Fixed Effects Model (FEM) based on the Hausman specification test. Diagnostic tests, including multicollinearity and robustness checks, ensure result validity. Data analysis is conducted with E-Views 13.

Findings: EPS and firm size significantly and positively influence share price, indicating investor preference for profitability and company scale. In contrast, audit firm size, firm age, leverage, and industry type show no significant effect, suggesting they are not primary drivers of stock performance. However, the interaction between firm size and industry type negatively affects share price, highlighting sectoral differences.

Originality/Value: This study enhances understanding of share price determinants in emerging markets, integrating firm attributes with sectoral considerations. The findings provide valuable insights for investors, corporate managers, and policymakers on stock valuation and regulatory strategies. It underscores the importance of financial performance indicators while advocating sector-specific policies to improve market efficiency. Future research should explore macroeconomic and governance factors influencing share price in Nigeria.

Keywords: Firm Attributes, Share Price, Earnings per Share, Firm Size, Audit Firm Size, Nigerian Stock Market, Financial and Non-Financial Sectors.

1. Introduction

The relationship between firm attributes and share price has remained a fundamental issue in financial and investment research. Investors rely on various firm-specific characteristics to assess the value and potential returns of their assets (Rehman, Kai & Xue, 2025). These attributes, including financial and non-financial factors, significantly influence share price movements in different sectors (Habib et al., 2022). In Nigeria, the stock market serves as a crucial platform for capital formation, and understanding the determinants of share prices is essential for market participants and policymakers.

Firm attributes encompass a range of factors such as profitability, leverage, firm size, liquidity, earnings quality, corporate governance, and market perception (Bodie, Kane, & Marcus, 2014). While financial sector firms, such as banks and insurance companies, rely heavily on regulatory frameworks and financial stability indicators (Seelanatha & Natoli, 2025), non-financial sector firms, including manufacturing and service-oriented businesses, are more influenced by operational efficiency, innovation, and consumer demand (Abedini Koshksaray et al., 2020). The variations in sectoral characteristics suggest that investors may evaluate financial and non-financial firms differently when making investment decisions (Bikas & Glinskytė, 2021).

Prior studies have extensively examined the impact of financial attributes such as earnings per share (EPS), price-to-earnings (P/E) ratio, and return on assets (ROA) on share price determination (AlAli, AlAskar & Aboualhasan, 2024; Otekunrin, et al., 2018). AlAli et al. (2024) reported a significant negative relationship between leverage and share price. On the other hand, Otekunrin et al. (2018) found a positive and significant relationship between EPS and share price. However, non-financial attributes, including corporate governance structure, board composition, and sustainability practices, have gained prominence as critical determinants of firm valuation (Thai et al., 2025; Larcker & Tayan, 2020; Bhagat & Bolton, 2008). This shift is particularly relevant in Nigeria's evolving investment landscape, where institutional investors are increasingly incorporating environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors in their decision-making process (Ojetunde et al., 2024).

Despite the growing body of literature, there remains a gap in understanding how investors weigh financial versus non-financial attributes when evaluating share prices across sectors in Nigeria. This study seeks to bridge this gap by analyzing the influence of firm attributes on the share prices of quoted financial and non-financial firms. The findings will provide insights into sector-specific investment behaviour, guiding both corporate managers and investors in strategic decision-making.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Several theories explain the relationship between firm attributes and share prices. The efficient market hypothesis (EMH) posits that share prices reflect all available information, meaning firm attributes are already priced in (Fama, 1970). Similarly, the signalling theory suggests that firms with strong attributes, such as good governance and profitability, signal their financial health to investors, thereby influencing share price movements (Spence, 1973). Agency theory also highlights the role of corporate governance in mitigating agency problems that could impact firm valuation (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Moreover, capital structure theory and the resource-based view (RBV) provide the theoretical foundation for this study.

The capital structure theory, particularly the Modigliani & Miller (1958) theorem and the trade-off theory, explains how firms balance debt and equity financing to maximize firm value. According to the trade-off theory, firms make capital structure decisions by weighing the benefits of debt (such as tax shields) against the costs (such as financial distress and bankruptcy risks). This study examines the relationship between leverage and share price, aligning with the argument that an optimal capital structure can enhance firm value and investor confidence.

On the other hand, the resource-based view (RBV) (Barney, 1991) emphasizes that firms achieve competitive advantage through unique resources and capabilities. Larger firms, with superior financial, human, and operational resources, may be better positioned to generate higher stock valuations. This perspective supports the investigation into firm size and its impact on share price, suggesting that well-resourced firms can achieve long-term financial sustainability and investor attraction. By integrating these theories, this study provides a robust framework for understanding how financial decisions and internal firm capabilities influence share price performance.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study examines the influence of six key firm attributes—age, audit firm size, firm size, earnings per share, leverage, and industry type—on the share price. Financial attributes play a significant role in share price determination (Saputra, 2022). Studies have established that earnings per share (EPS) and price-to-earnings (P/E) ratio are critical metrics in investor evaluations (Odoemelam et al. 2019; Otekunrin, et al., 2018). Return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) have also been linked to stock performance, as higher profitability tends to attract investors (Atmariansi & Agustia, 2024). Leverage ratios, such as debt-to-equity (D/E), provide insight into a firm's financial stability, impacting investor sentiment and stock prices (Nukala & Prasada Rao, 2021).

2.2.1 Firm Age and Share Price

Firm age is a critical determinant of corporate stability, reputation, and investor confidence (Cancela et al., 2020). Older firms tend to have established operational structures, market credibility, and accumulated experience, which enhance investor trust and contribute to higher share prices (Mansur & Tangl, 2018). The Resource-Based View (RBV) suggests that older firms accumulate valuable intangible resources such as brand equity, customer loyalty, and managerial expertise, which can lead to long-term financial sustainability and positive stock performance (Clulow et al., 2003).

However, according to Coad et al. (2022), younger firms often exhibit higher growth potential and innovation capabilities, attracting speculative investors who seek rapid capital appreciation. Empirical studies by Dewi (2019) and Pati et al. (2018) show that while older firms may benefit from stability, younger firms often outperform in dynamic industries due to their agility and growth prospects.

H1: Firm age has a significant positive impact on share price.

2.2.2 Audit Firm Size and Share Price

The size of an audit firm plays a crucial role in determining financial reporting credibility, investor confidence, and firm valuation (Pham, Nguyen & Tran, 2025). Large audit firms, particularly the Big Four (Deloitte, PwC, EY, and KPMG), are associated with higher audit quality, reduced earnings manipulation, and enhanced financial transparency (Beisland et

al., 2018; DeAngelo, 1981). The Agency Theory supports this notion, as high-quality audits help mitigate information asymmetry between managers and investors, thereby improving market efficiency (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

Previous studies by Yahaya, (2024) and Kurt et al. (2024) demonstrate that firms audited by top-tier audit firms experience lower financial restatement risks and higher stock market valuations. However, some scholars argue that audit firm size alone may not significantly influence share price if other governance mechanisms, such as internal controls and board oversight, are robust (El-Deeb, Alarabi & Mohamed, 2024).

H2: Audit firm size has a significant positive impact on share price.

2.2.3 Firm Size and Share Price

Firm size is a fundamental attribute that influences financial stability, market dominance, and investor confidence (Handoyo et al., 2023). Larger firms typically have diversified revenue streams, better access to capital markets, and lower bankruptcy risk, making them attractive to investors (Sukesti et al., 2021; Ishak & Selamat, 2024). The Signaling Theory suggests that firm size serves as a signal of corporate stability and competitive advantage, leading to positive investor perceptions and higher share prices (Connelly et al., 2025). Empirical studies by Lee et al. (2025) and Irawan et al. (2025) confirm that larger firms tend to have lower market volatility and stronger stock price resilience during economic downturns. However, the Size Effect Hypothesis suggests that smaller firms may offer higher growth potential and stock price appreciation, albeit with greater risk (Audretsch et al., 2024; Sala-Rios, 2024).

H3: Firm size has a significant positive relationship with share price.

2.2.4 Earnings Per Share (EPS) and Share Price

EPS is one of the most widely used indicators of firm performance and stock valuation (Abbas et al., 2024; Puspitasari et al., 2025). Higher EPS suggests strong profitability and efficient resource utilization, leading to greater investor confidence and stock price appreciation (Al-Shattarat, 2021; Odoemelam et al. 2019). The Dividend Discount Model (DDM) supports this relationship, as higher earnings often lead to higher dividends, enhancing stock desirability (Heller, 2021).

Empirical evidence from studies by Barth et al. (2020) and Barth, Beaver, & Landsman (2001) indicates that earnings announcements significantly influence stock price movements, with positive earnings surprises leading to share price increases. Conversely, firms with declining EPS often experience negative investor sentiment and stock depreciation (Mashoka, 2025).

H4: Earnings per share has a significant positive impact on share price.

2.2.5 Leverage and Share Price

Leverage, measured by the debt-to-equity ratio, plays a dual role in corporate finance (Essel, 2025). Moderate leverage can enhance financial performance and shareholder returns through the Tax Shield Effect, where interest expenses reduce taxable income (Modigliani & Miller, 1958). However, excessive leverage increases financial distress risk, reducing investor confidence and leading to stock price declines (Acheampong et al., 2014). Empirical studies by Cai & Zhang (2011) and Altman et al. (2019) confirm that while leverage can improve

stock valuation at optimal levels, firms with excessive debt tend to suffer lower stock price performance due to increased bankruptcy concerns.

H5: Leverage has a significant negative relationship with share price.

2.2.6 Industry Type and Share Price

Financial firms operate under stricter regulations and risk management frameworks (Huang et al., 2022), while non-financial firms are driven by consumer demand and operational efficiency (Laghari et al., 2023). These sectoral differences influence share price behaviour (Uwuigbe et al., 2015). Beyond financial attributes, non-financial factors also influence share prices. Corporate governance structures, including board independence and ownership concentration, have been associated with stock valuation (Uwuigbe et al., 2015). Similarly, firms with strong environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices tend to attract institutional investors, reflecting positively on their share prices (Adegboyegun et al., 2020). Innovation, brand reputation, and management efficiency further contribute to stock market performance in non-financial sectors (Hoffmann & Fieseler, 2012; Cumby & Conrod, 2001). The evaluation of firm attributes varies between financial and non-financial sectors. Financial firms are heavily regulated, and their stock prices are influenced by regulatory compliance, capital adequacy, and risk exposure (Bodie et al., 2014). In contrast, non-financial firms' share prices are shaped by factors such as supply chain efficiency, product innovation, and market expansion (Cao et al., 2022). Investors apply different valuation techniques based on these sectoral differences, influencing stock price dynamics.

H6: Industry type (financial vs. non-financial) significantly moderates the relationship between firm attributes and share price.

2.5 Empirical Review

Empirical studies on Nigerian firms reveal mixed results regarding the impact of firm attributes on share prices. Abdullahi et al. (2020) found that financial metrics such as ROA and EPS significantly affect stock performance in Nigerian banks. Uwuigbe et al. (2015) observed that board composition and CEO duality influence the share prices of manufacturing firms. Akbar & Putri (2024) revealed no significant relationship between leverage and share price. Similarly, Omri, Neffati & Guenichi (2025) indicated a statistically significant negative relationship between leverage and stock price for companies that fall below a certain size threshold. However, once firms surpass this threshold, they tend to experience a notable improvement in both accounting and financial performance. This suggests that while excessive debt can hinder smaller firms, larger firms may leverage debt more effectively to drive growth and enhance profitability. A study by Mansur & Tangl (2018) examined the relationship between leverage and firm performance, finding that while higher leverage can enhance returns due to tax benefits, it also increases financial risk, which can negatively affect share prices. Research by Abdullah et al. (2015) investigated how leverage influences stock price volatility. The findings suggest that increased leverage leads to higher volatility in share prices, as the fixed interest obligations amplify the impact of earnings fluctuations on equity holders.

While existing studies have explored firm attributes and share price relationships, few have explicitly compared investor evaluations across financial and non-financial sectors in Nigeria. This study aims to fill this gap by providing a sectoral analysis of how financial and non-

financial attributes influence share prices, offering insights for investors, policymakers, and corporate decision-makers.

2. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts an ex post facto research design, which is appropriate for analyzing historical data to establish relationships between firm attributes and share price. Ex post facto research enables the study of cause-and-effect relationships where variables cannot be manipulated (Varghese, 2025). Given that financial data and firm characteristics are obtained from secondary sources, this design is most suitable for drawing empirical inferences.

3.2 Population and Sample Size

The study population comprises all quoted firms in Nigeria, listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of the study period. Given the variability across industries, the sample includes firms from both the financial and non-financial sectors to ensure sectoral representation. The sampling technique used is purposive sampling, which selects firms based on data availability and consistency over the study period. The final sample consists of 1,800 firm-year observations (100 firms), ensuring a robust dataset for statistical analysis.

3.3 Data and Sources

Secondary data were obtained from annual reports and financial statements of quoted 100 sampled firms, as well as NGX Factbook and audited financial disclosures. The data spanned 18 years (2006 to 2023), ensuring a longitudinal approach to analyzing firm attributes and their impact on share price. The financial indicators were extracted from audited reports of the sampled firms, to ensure reliability and minimize reporting bias (DeFond & Zhang, 2014).

3.4 Variables and Measurement

The study examines the impact of firm attributes on share price. The variables are categorized as follows:

3.4.1 Dependent Variable

Share Price (SP): Following Odoemelam et al. (2019) and Abbas et al. (2024), SP is measured as the closing share price of firms at the end of the financial year, obtained from NGX records.

3.4.2 Independent Variables

Firm Age (Age): In line with the studies by Tatiana et al. (2013) and Ofoegbu & Odoemelam (2018), firm age is a dummy variable where 1 represents firms older (if the company's leverage is $\geq 20\%$) and 0 otherwise.

Audit Firm Size (AFS): Following Yahaya, (2024), Kurt et al. (2024), and DeAngelo (1981), AFS is a dummy variable where 1 represents firms audited by a Big Four audit firm and 0 otherwise.

Earnings Per Share (EPS): Following Lee (2025), EPS is net earnings available to shareholders divided by the number of outstanding shares.

Firm Size (FS): Measured as the natural logarithm of total assets, a common proxy for firm size in financial studies (Dang et al., 2018; Alabdulkarim et al., 2024).

Leverage (Lev): Following Odoemelam et al., (2019), Lev is the ratio of total debt to total assets, representing financial risk exposure.

Industry Type (IT): A dummy variable where 1 represents financial sector firms and 0 represents non-financial firms (Rajan & Zingales, 1995).

3.5 Model Specification

To examine the relationship between firm attributes and share price, the following multiple regression model is specified:

$$SP_{it} = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 Age_{it} + \gamma_2 AFS_{it} + \gamma_3 EPS_{it} + \gamma_4 FS_{it} + \gamma_5 LEV_{it} + \gamma_6 IT_{it} + \gamma_7 Age_{it} * IT_{it} + \gamma_8 AFS_{it} * IT_{it} + \gamma_9 EPS_{it} * IT_{it} + \gamma_{10} FS_{it} * IT_{it} + \gamma_{11} LEV_{it} * IT_{it} + \mu_i + \lambda_t + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where Age is the company age, AFS is the audit firm size dummy (1 for Big 4 audit firms, 0 otherwise), EPS is the earnings per share, FS is the firm size (natural log of total assets), LEV is the leverage, IT is the industry type, Age*IT is the interaction of company age and industry type, AFS*IT is the interaction of audit firm size and industry type, EPS*IT is the interaction of earnings per share and industry type, FS*IT is the interaction of firm size and industry type and LEV*IT is the interaction of leverage and industry type.

3.6 Estimation Technique

Applying the panel data modelling, this study used the Fixed Effect Model as the estimation technique. Hausman specification test suggests using the Fixed Effect Model because we rejected the null hypothesis. Results regarding the Hausman specification test have been presented in Table 4.

3.6.1 Diagnostic Tests

To assess multicollinearity among the independent variables, we conducted a test using EViews 13, following the guidelines of Gujarati & Porter (2009). The results, presented in Table 3, confirm that no multicollinearity issues were detected among the independent variables.

Following the robustness checks, various diagnostic tests were performed to determine the most appropriate estimation technique for the dataset. Specifically, the Hausman specification test was applied to compare the Fixed Effects Model (FEM) and Random Effects Model (REM). The test results indicated a p-value of 0.0000, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0), which suggests that the Random Effects Model is appropriate. Consequently, the Fixed Effects Model was deemed more suitable for this study. The output for the Hausman specification test is provided in Table 4, where the p-value falls below the 5% significance threshold, reinforcing the preference for the Fixed Effects approach.

4 Analysis and results

This study examines both financial and non-financial firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX), as outlined in the methodology section. A total of 100 publicly listed companies were sampled over 18 years (2006–2023). To evaluate the relationship between firm attributes and share price, the dataset was analyzed using EViews 13, a widely used

statistical software for econometric modeling. The findings provide insights into how various firm characteristics influence stock market performance within the Nigerian capital market.

4.1 Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics in Table 1, provide insights into the characteristics of the 100 firms analyzed in the study. Firm age has a high mean of 0.92, indicating that most firms are well-established. Audit firm size (AFS) shows that 60% of firms are audited by a Big Four firm, suggesting a relatively strong external audit presence. Earnings per share (EPS) has a mean of 1.35 but a high standard deviation (6.77), reflecting significant variability, with some firms experiencing extreme losses (minimum -211.99) or high profits (maximum 70.54). Firm size (FS) has a mean of 9.88 with moderate dispersion (2.41), showing that most firms are mid-sized. Industry type has a mean of 0.32, indicating that approximately 32% of firms belong to a specific sector (financial or non-financial). Leverage (Lev) has a mean of 0.63, with some firms carrying no debt while others have extremely high leverage (maximum 29.00). Share price (SP) exhibits substantial variation, with an average of 26.22 and a very high standard deviation (94.44), indicating that while most firms have moderate stock prices, some have exceptionally high values (maximum 1,487). These statistics suggest considerable diversity in firm attributes, which may significantly influence share price behaviour across sectors.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Age	1800	0	1	.92	.276
AFS	1800	0	1	.60	.490
EPS	1800	-211.990	70.540	1.3519	6.7700
FS	1800	4.33	30.65	9.8797	2.4153
IT	1800	0	1	.32	.465
Lev	1800	.000	29.000	.63205	1.1980
SP	1800	.41	1487.00	26.216	94.436
Valid N (listwise)	1800				

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Table 2 shows the correlation results reveal significant relationships between firm attributes and industry type. Firm age is negatively correlated with industry type ($r = -0.214$, $p < 0.01$), implying that older firms are more likely to be in a specific industry, possibly the non-financial sector. Audit firm size (AFS) shows a significant positive correlation with firm size ($r = 0.361$, $p < 0.01$) and industry type ($r = 0.167$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that larger firms and firms in a specific industry are more likely to engage Big Four audit firms, supporting DeAngelo's (1981) argument that larger firms prefer high-quality auditors. Earnings per share (EPS) is positively correlated with firm size ($r = 0.178$, $p < 0.01$) but negatively correlated with industry type ($r = -0.065$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that larger firms tend to have higher earnings, but financial sector firms may experience lower EPS levels, aligning with the findings of Fama and French (1992) on firm size and profitability. Leverage (Lev) is negatively correlated with industry type ($r = -0.059$, $p < 0.05$), meaning that firms in a specific sector (likely financial firms) have lower leverage, consistent with Modigliani and Miller's (1958) capital structure theory, which suggests that industry characteristics influence debt financing. Firm size has a strong positive correlation with industry type ($r = 0.324$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that financial firms are generally larger, in line with the resource-based view (Barney, 1991). Overall, the findings reinforce theoretical perspectives that firm

characteristics influence financial decisions and industry placement while highlighting sectoral differences in financial structure and audit preferences.

Table 2: Correlations

		Age	AFS	EPS	FS	Lev	IT
Age	<i>r</i>	1.000					
	<i>P</i>						
AFS	<i>r</i>	.001	1.000				
	<i>P</i>	.954					
EPS	<i>r</i>	.014	.075**	1.000			
	<i>P</i>	.549	.002				
FS	<i>r</i>	.015	.361**	.178**	1.000		
	<i>P</i>	.530	.000	.000			
Lev	<i>r</i>	.014	.010	-.015	.024	1.000	
	<i>P</i>	.547	.681	.529	.303		
IT	<i>r</i>	-.214**	.167**	-.065**	.324**	-.059*	1.000
	<i>P</i>	.000	.000	.006	.000	.012	
	<i>N</i>	1800	1800	1800	1800	1800	1800

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Notes: SP, share price; AGE, firm age; AFS, audit firm size; FS, firm size; LEV, leverage; IT, industry type; r, coefficient; p, probability value (p-value)

4.3 Multicollinearity Test

The collinearity statistics from Table 3 indicate that multicollinearity is not a major concern in the regression model. Tolerance values for all independent variables are well above the critical threshold of 0.10, and the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values are all below 10, with the highest being 1.314 for firm size (FS). This suggests that the predictor variables—age, audit firm size (AFS), earnings per share (EPS), firm size (FS), leverage (Lev), and industry type—are not highly correlated with one another, ensuring stable and reliable regression estimates (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). The relatively low VIF values indicate that each explanatory variable provides unique information about the dependent variable (share price), supporting the robustness of the model (Becker et al., 2015). Therefore, the absence of multicollinearity strengthens the validity of the regression results and enhances the credibility of the study's findings regarding the relationship between firm attributes and share price

Table 3: Multicollinearity results

	I/VIF	VIF
Age	.946	1.057
AFS	.867	1.154
EPS	.950	1.053
FS	.761	1.314
Lev	.993	1.007
IT	.825	1.213
Mean VIF	-	1.133

Notes: AGE, firm age; AFS, audit firm size; EPS, earnings per share; FS, firm size; Lev, leverage; IT, industry type.

4.3.1 Regression Result

The Hausman test result ($\chi^2 = 109.731$, $p = 0.0000$) presented in Table 4 confirms that the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) is more appropriate than the Random Effect Model (REM) for this study, reinforcing the importance of firm-specific attributes in explaining share price variations. Therefore, interpretations and discussion of findings are based on FEM.

The Fixed Effect Model (FEM) results provide critical insights into the relationship between firm attributes and share price, in line with the study's hypotheses. The R^2 value of 0.7795 and the adjusted R^2 of 0.7651 indicate that approximately 77.95% of the variations in share price are explained by the firm attributes, showing a strong explanatory power. Among the independent variables, earnings per share (EPS) (coef. = 1.3242, $p = 0.0000$) and firm size (FS) (coef. = 5.1749, $p = 0.0000$) have statistically significant positive effects on share price, supporting H4 and H3, respectively. This suggests that higher earnings per share and larger firm sizes contribute positively to share price performance, as larger firms tend to be more stable and profitable, attracting investor confidence. However, firm age (coef. = 2.4657, $p = 0.7516$) and leverage (coef. = 0.0623, $p = 0.9496$) show no significant impact on share price, indicating that these factors may not directly influence stock valuation in the sampled firms, contradicting H1 and H5.

Audit firm size (AFS) has a positive coefficient (6.4815) but is not statistically significant ($p = 0.2641$), suggesting that while engaging larger audit firms may enhance credibility, it does not necessarily lead to higher share prices in this dataset, which weakens H2. Industry type (IT) also presents an insignificant but large positive coefficient (66.410, $p = 0.2010$), indicating potential sectoral differences in share price determinants, though it does not strongly support H6. Interaction effects reveal mixed findings; FS*IT (-7.0516, $p = 0.0005$) is statistically significant and negative, suggesting that firm size affects share price differently across financial and non-financial sectors, providing partial support for the moderating role of industry type. However, interactions between EPS*IT (-0.3906, $p = 0.7475$) and AFS*IT (1.1916, $p = 0.9143$) remain insignificant, indicating that the relationship between earnings per share, audit firm size, and share price does not vary significantly across industries.

The F-statistic (54.287, $p = 0.0000$) confirms the overall model significance, meaning that firm attributes collectively influence share price performance. However, the Durbin-Watson statistic (0.7134) suggests the presence of serial correlation, which may need further robustness checks. However, the multicollinearity test was not a major concern (Table 3). Overall, the findings provide strong empirical support for EPS and firm size as key determinants of share price, while audit firm size, leverage, and industry type show weak or insignificant effects, implying that investors may prioritize financial fundamentals over external audit quality and sectoral classifications when evaluating share prices of Nigerian quoted firms.

Table 4: Random-Effects & Fixed Effects panel regression of Share Price on Firm Attributes

Variables	Random Effect Model (REM)					Fixed Effect Model (FEM)				
	Coef.	t-value	SE	P-value	Sig	Coef.	t-value	SE	P-value	Sig
SP										
Age	3.1392	0.4068	7.7166	0.6842		2.4657	0.3165	7.7882	0.7516	
AFS	12.154	2.2744	5.3439	0.0231	**	6.4815	1.1170	5.802	0.2641	
EPS	1.5648	8.0774	0.1937	0.0000	***	1.3242	6.7837	0.1952	0.0000	***
FS	6.7559	5.0098	1.358	0.0000	***	5.1749	3.5491	1.4580	0.0000	***
LEV	0.0771	0.0784	0.9840	0.9375		0.0623	0.0632	0.9871	0.9496	
IT	57.910	2.4024	24.104	0.0164	**	66.410	1.2792	51.914	0.2010	
AFS*IT	-4.258	-0.415	10.238	0.6775		1.1916	0.1076	11.069	0.9143	
Age*IT	-3.254	-0.292	11.111	0.7696		-2.356	-0.210	11.218	0.8336	
EPS*IT	-0.6444	-0.5347	1.2050	0.5929		-0.3906	-0.3220	1.2129	0.7475	
FS*IT	-8.3492	-4.384	1.904	0.0000	***	-7.0516	-3.4791	2.0268	0.0005	***
LEV*IT	5.4565	0.4522	12.012	0.6497		4.1707	0.3402	12.258	0.7337	
cons	-40.747	-2.541	18.034	0.0111	**	-29.620	-1.3010	22.766	0.7516	
R ²	0.0570					0.7795				
Adj R ²	0.0512					0.7651				
F-stat.	9.8407					54.287				
Prob (F-statistic)	0.0000					0.0000				
DW	0.6459					0.7134				
Hausman Test	Ch ² (109.731) Prob>ch ² = 0.0000									
No of Obs.	1800					1800				

Notes: SP, share price; AGE, firm age; AFS, audit firm size; FS, firm size; LEV, leverage; IT, Industry type

5 Discussion

This study's findings align with theoretical and empirical literature on the determinants of share price, particularly in emerging markets like Nigeria. The positive and significant impact of earnings per share (EPS) on share price supports the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) by Fama (1970), which asserts that stock prices reflect all available information, including earnings performance. This finding is consistent with prior empirical studies (Otekunrin, et al., 2018; Uwuigbe et al., 2016) highlights EPS as a strong predictor of stock market valuation. Investors often perceive higher earnings as an indicator of firm profitability and sustainability, leading to increased demand and higher stock prices.

Similarly, firm size (FS) exhibits a positive and significant influence on share price, reinforcing the signaling theory (Spence, 1973) and empirical findings by Usman & Yahaya (2023) and Abdullahi et al. (2023). Larger firms are perceived as more stable, diversified, and less prone to financial distress, making them attractive to investors. This result aligns with the work of Adeniyi & Abiodun (2020), who found that larger firms in Nigeria's financial sector tend to have higher share prices due to economies of scale, stronger market presence, and better access to capital. However, the study contradicts the findings of Okoro et al. (2022), which suggested that firm size had an insignificant effect on share prices in certain sectors.

On the other hand, audit firm size (AFS) does not significantly impact share price, contrary to the expectations of the Agency Theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). While previous studies (Adeyemi & Fagbemi, 2010) have argued that firms audited by Big Four firms signal higher financial reporting credibility, this study suggests that in Nigeria, investors may not strongly emphasise audit firm reputation when making investment decisions. Likewise, firm age (Age) and leverage (Lev) exhibit no significant relationship with share price, which is in contrast to

the findings of Matemilola et al. (2017), who reported that older firms tend to have more stable stock prices. The insignificance of leverage aligns with the work of Salawu & Agboola (2008), who found that in emerging economies, leverage may not always be a reliable predictor of share price due to varying capital structures and investor risk perceptions.

Finally, though positive, the industry type (IT) variable lacks statistical significance, suggesting that sectoral classification alone does not determine share price variations in Nigeria. This contrasts with the findings of Aobdia & Shroff (2017), who observed that financial sector firms tend to have higher share price responses due to regulatory oversight and investor confidence. However, the significant negative interaction effect between firm size and industry type (FS*IT) suggests that firm size influences share price differently across financial and non-financial sectors, supporting the notion that industry characteristics moderate firm attributes' impact on stock valuation.

In summary, this study confirms EPS and firm size as critical drivers of share price in Nigeria, while audit firm size, firm age, leverage, and industry type show limited or no influence. These findings contribute to the broader literature by reinforcing the role of financial fundamentals over non-financial attributes in share price determination, particularly in emerging economies.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examines the relationship between firm attributes and share price in Nigerian quoted firms, with a focus on both financial and non-financial sectors. The findings reveal that earnings per share (EPS) and firm size (FS) have significant positive effects on share price, highlighting their importance as key drivers of stock market valuation. However, audit firm size (AFS), firm age (Age), leverage (Lev), and industry type (IT) do not exhibit significant effects on share price, suggesting that investors in Nigeria may prioritize financial performance indicators over external audit quality, firm maturity, or sectoral classification. Additionally, the interaction between firm size and industry type (FS*IT) is significant and negative, indicating that firm size influences share price differently across sectors. These results align with existing financial theories, such as the efficient market hypothesis (EMH) and signalling theory, which emphasize the role of financial performance in investment decisions.

6.1 Practical Implications

The findings have important implications for various stakeholders in the Nigerian capital market. The study provides empirical evidence that earnings per share (EPS) is a strong determinant of the share price. Investors should prioritize firms with strong earnings performance when making investment decisions. Additionally, firm size matters, particularly in distinguishing firms across financial and non-financial sectors. The findings suggest that managers should focus on improving financial performance, particularly earnings per share, as it significantly impacts stock valuation. Moreover, given the limited influence of audit firm size on share price, firms may choose auditors based on factors beyond market perception, such as cost-effectiveness and industry expertise. Regulators, such as the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) and the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NGX), should ensure that listed firms maintain transparent financial reporting practices to enhance investor confidence. Given that industry type alone does not significantly influence share price, policies promoting financial disclosures across all sectors could improve market efficiency.

6.2 Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i.) Firms should adopt strategic financial management practices aimed at increasing earnings per share (EPS), such as effective cost management, revenue diversification, and operational efficiency.
- ii.) Although audit firm size does not significantly impact share price, firms should maintain high-quality financial reporting to build investor trust and improve market credibility.
- iii.) Investors should be educated on the key financial indicators that drive share price movements, such as EPS and firm size, to make informed investment decisions rather than relying on non-financial factors.
- iv.) Regulators should develop sector-based financial disclosure policies that enhance transparency across both financial and non-financial sectors to bridge the gap in investor perception and share price valuation.
- v.) Future studies should explore other macroeconomic and corporate governance factors that may influence share prices, such as inflation, interest rates, and board characteristics, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of stock valuation in Nigeria.

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